

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.	B503		
Date:	25/01/10		
Take Off:	10:43:22Z	Z	Z
Landing:	16:09:29Z	Z	Z
Flight Time:	5h 26m 07s	h m s	h m s

Campaign: CONSTRAIN

Operating Area: Orkney area

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight
2	Co	Alan Foster	Directflight
3	CCM	Robbie Voden	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Richard Cotton	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / AVAPS	Angela Dean	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	FAAM
8	CVI / Mission Scientist Training	Kirsty McBeath	Met Office
9	Mission Scientist 2	Keith Bower	Manchester Uni
10	Mini-LIDAR	Dave Pollard	Met Office
11	Manchester Cloud	James Dorsey	Manchester Uni
12	CVI2	Paul Barratt	Met Office
13	ARIES	Clare Lee	Met Office
14	SID-2 / SID-3	Joseph Ulanowski	Hertfordshire Uni
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			

	Log Sheet included
Y	Flight Folder Front Page
Y	Flight Summary
	Met Office 0600 UTC Actual Surface analysis (ASXX) chart
Y	Track Plot (GIN or GPS)
	DFLFliteStar planned track
Y	Brief
	Mission Scientist 1's logs
	Mission Scientist 2's logs
	De-brief
	ViRC chat log
	Flight Manager's Instrument Status log
Y	Flight Manager's Faults/Incidents log
Y	Pre-flight log
Y	Core Chemistry / NOx / TDLAS
Y	Cloud Physics In Flight
	Cloud Physics Processing
Y	AVAPS
	PSAP log
	Filters
	Printed Plots
Y	Screengrabs (Lidar)
	Planning charts or plots
	Images Emailed To BAe146 In Flight

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
R0	2010-01-25	Mo Smith	Initial version
R1			
r2			

B503 09:25:37-16:13:33

B503 25 January 2010

Sortie S4: Snow evolution in deep Altostratus and Cirrostratus.

Deep Altostratus and Cirrostratus layers associated with fronts are required for observations of snow evolution when aggregation and sedimentation dominates the cloud evolution rather than ice nucleation or dynamics.

Ice crystal shape or capacitance factor controls how efficiently the ice crystal acts as a source or sink of water vapour. Depositional growth rate.

Weather

Ahead of warm front.

Sortie location

North coast Scotland.

Sortie summary

Perform a Lagrangian descent during which the aircraft drifts with the horizontal wind and descending at a rate similar to the mass weighted fallspeed of snow particles. Lagrangian descent from cloud top to the altitude when all precipitation has evaporated.

Sortie detail

- 1) **Transit** to operating area at best-range speed and altitude.
- 2) **Profile ascent** through cloud until 2000ft above cloud top or maximum altitude. During profile, determine average wind orientation.
- 3) Identify the altitude and location of start of Lagrangian descent. All runs are orientated across the determined wind direction.
- 4) **Dropsonde run**: Perform straight and level 2000ft above cloud top. Lidar reports average cloud top height. Drop sonde near descent location.
- 5) Descend into cloud layer.
- 6) **Cloud penetration runs**: Perform a descending Lagrangian descent, drifting with the horizontal wind to repeatedly sample cloud. The flight path is a race-track where one side is a straight and level run (5 min) and the other side is a profile descent (400ft/min). Initial turn direction is specified by mission scientist.
- 7) **Return transit** at best range speed.

Instrument requirements

Dropsonde launch locations critical, must be in region of Lagrangian descent. **CVI** operated continuously in Counter-Flow mode. No varying cut-size or changing to aerosol mode.

Nevezorov zeroed once only when at high level early in flight.

Lidar operated to identify cloud base. No varying integration time or changing the display.

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B503

Date: 25 January 2010

Project: CONSTRAIN

Location: Orkney

Start End

Time	Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
093441		Start-Up	-.56 kft	260	55'30.33N, 4'35.86W
103829		ASP	-.58 kft	062	Open
104322		T/O	1.3 kft	123	Prestwick
104734		JW/Nevz	5.4 kft	306	Zero
105357		Video	11.2 kft	341	Start recording
113030		Event	31.0 kft	309	Start WxRx, 3min ahead of Horace
114909		Sonde	32.0 kft	233	Launch #001
114930		Event	32.0 kft	233	Contrailing
115356		Event	32.0 kft	343	Embellished by F3
115506	120004	Run 1.1	32.0 kft	051	
120307	120752	Profile 1.1	32.0 - 30.0 kft	230	400fpm
121017	121517	Run 1.2	30.1 - 30.0 kft	050	
121732	122234	Profile 1.2	30.1 - 28.1 kft	227	400fpm
122448	122949	Run 1.3	28.1 - 28.0 kft	053	
123159	123704	Profile 1.3	28.1 - 26.1 kft	229	
123803		JW & Nevz	26.0 kft	321	Zero Cal
123908	124509	Run 1.4	26.1 - 26.0 kft	046	
124558	125757	Profile 2	26.5 - 33.0 kft	055	
130355	130856	Profile 2	33.0 - 34.0 kft	027	Contrailing 130551
131646	131852	Profile 3	34.3 - 35.0 kft	268	
131900	132736	Run 2.0	35.1 - 35.0 kft	263	
132742	133213	Run 2.1	35.1 - 35.0 kft	059	
133000		Sonde	35.0 kft	057	Launch #02
133518	134011	Profile 4.1	35.1 - 33.1 kft	230	400fpm
134230	134756	Run 2.2	33.1 - 33.0 kft	048	
135025	135527	Profile 4.2	33.1 - 31.1 kft	231	Contrailing ,stopped at FL314
135740	140240	Run 2.3	31.1 kft	048	
140452	140952	Profile 4.3	31.1 - 29.0 kft	228	
141204	141704	Run 2.4	29.1 - 29.0 kft	048	
141913	142345	Profile 4.4	29.1 - 27.1 kft	229	
142557	143153	Run 2.5	27.1 - 27.0 kft	049	
143350	143901	Profile 4.5	27.1 - 25.1 kft	226	
144106	144638	Run 2.6	25.1 kft	047	
144835	145308	Profile 4.6	25.1 - 23.1 kft	227	
145507	150113	Run 2.7	23.1 kft	046	
150258	150802	Profile 4,7	23.1 - 28.0 kft	220	

Mission Scientist's Log

IN CIRROUS
SEA: SNOW EVOLUTION & AHEAD OF WARM FRONT,

Flight No **B503** Date 25/1/10 Name R. COTTON Page 1 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					7/8 Sc, no precip
104250*					Take off Prestwick
104530		3800ft			Enter cloud during climb.
104630					Top 5200ft, 1/8 Ci above
110238		FL230			Wind 13m/s 2° Tc: -32°C, Ta: -54°C
					ci ahead and to east.
	climb to to try and reach Ci	FL270		(CVI)	Speed run require cloud.) Tc: -39°C, Ta: -57°C
	climb to	FL290		nearly	ISA atm Tc: -44°C Ta: -58°C
					Wind 29m/s 2°
~1115	(Pl obs) few particles			ci ahead	looks uniform, no particular direction looks deeper, as carry on this direction.
	climb to	FL310		SID	seeing in at FL295
112130		FL310			Ready for CVI speed run Tc: -49°C, Ta: -49°C
					Wind 35m/s at 345° 75° orientable
				Lidar FL 295 (cloud base)	
112045				Lidar FL 270	
113500		speed	210		after this, mark pt and d. spiral descent.
1136		cloud base		FL 270.	
1142		Climbing to	drop	side to	FL 320
114910		sonde launch			run for further 2min, then start first descent
		FL320			
				Tc:	-52°C, Ta: -52°C
				We are	contrailing.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.507** Date 25/1/10 Name R. Roth Page 2 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					waiting for ATC clearance to turn left.
115506	R1.1 _{st}	FL220		start of spiral.	
				In ci,	cannot see top.
					Tc: -52°C, Ta: -52°C
		LIDAR		FL260	cloud base
1201	0-6	on ground			AIR10 seeing more cirrus
120302	P1.1 _{st}	FL220			wind 30kts at 335°
		LIDAR		FL260	cloud base
120755	P1.1 _{end}	FL300			can see ground.
121018	R1.2 _{st}	FL300			Tc = -46°C Ta = -46°C wind 337°
					can see ground below so no cloud layer.
121520	R1.2 _{end}				after this descent will reposition NE.
121730	P1.2 _{st}	FL300			
122949	R1.3 _{end}	FL220			LIDAR reports base FL270 end (260-124) ie sublimating at eastern end.
					Tc = -42°C, Ta = -43°C
123157	P1.3 _{st}	FL280			wind 350° 21kts
		FL265			Tc = -39°C, Ta = -42°C
123764	P1.3 _{end}	FL260			cloud thicker to right (north of our pt).
					Tc = -37°C, Ta = -45°C
					too dry here.
					✓ end descent, and start
					Profile 21:10-1000 ft/m

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B⁵⁰** Date 15/1/10 Name R. Coates Page 3 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
125757	P2				Re-position at science point to NE.
					in cloud
130555	R2	FL340			Use LIDAR to see base cloud thinning, so fly to west towards thicker cloud. FL350.
					Prepare to land.
	R2	FL350			FL300-310 thickest part cloud base lowering.
1324					LIDAR base FL250
					wind orient about 225° <u>060 gms</u>
132725	R2.5t				LIDAR run also first spiral run.
					59° 00.8, 7° 04.4 at 1324. wind 220°.
133000					drop sonde FL350 Tc: -60°C, Td: -60°C
133213	R2.1ea				LIDAR base FL240.
					drop sonde reports base around 400ms ~ FL240
90 min on task left.					
134013	P2.1ea	FL330			Tc: -54°C, Td: -54°C
1344					ZDC back on but noisy at ^{consider time}
134800	R2.2ea				LIDAR: main cloud below FL300
135025	P2.2t	FL330			peaking at FL310, then back to FL240.
	P2.2ea	FL310			LIDAR / CPU reports cloud thinning near western end.
135740	R2.2t	FL310			Tc: -48°C Td: -49°C
	LIDAR	observed			high return 'cell' below (FL290?)

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Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B503** Date 15/1/10 Name R. Cotton Page 4 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
141400		FL290			Tc: -44°C Td: -45°C
141704	R2.4 _{end}	FL290			
141920	P2.4 _{st}	FL290			CPI notes sublimation near eastern end of run
					LIDAR confirmed high-intensity return.
	(move by 1min eastward)				shorten this to 30 sec extend next run by 20 sec } increase rate of desc.
4m- 142245	P2.4 _{end}	4.20 min run		FL290	
142555	R2.5 _{st}	5.20 min run			Tc: -39°C, Td: -39°C
					8700 ft below at eastern end, 0/10 below at western end
					LIDAR/CPI this level. look FL290
	R2.5 _{end}				6 min dash ACE
					feature is at eastern end
					and extend again
	P2.5 _{end}	FL250			same position now } after discussion
					change mind again
144104	R2.6	5.20 min run			Tc: -35°C, Td: -36°C
144308					CPI reports in feature, also some turbulence, so in fall structure etc
	P2.6 _{st}	4.20 profile			
145025	FL243				Tc: -30°C, Td: -45°C dry
	P2.6 _{end}	FL200			
270 PL250 20- 145507	R2.7 _{st}	FL200			6 min run
					4 min profile
					no particles detected. as end of run.
					and profile up
					1000 ft/min.

10 min/profile + 5 min = 15 min //

1500

ARIES flight log

Flight: B503

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Date: 25/01/10

Operator(s): CAROL LEE

Res:

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: CONSTRAIN N. Scotland (Cirrus ahead of warm front.)

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
11:05		C Hal		C	70.9	31.2	HC cal 1min.
11:12:18	transit 28 kft.	CAV NZ		0			CAVIAR NZ 30s 30s CH, 30s N, 30s Z repeated. thin Ci above, sheets StW with some large holes at 5kft. In base of Ci cloud. Clear below
11:18:04	29655A						Starting to lead over StW.
11:25:45		Z long					Zenith long on 1min. *
11:26:28							Turning to right left.
11:28:06							* 30s CH, 1min Z repeated.
	31 kft.						Cirrus thickening above +
11:32:45	CAV NZ	CAV NZ	0		70.9	30.4	below CAVIAR NZ 30s 30s CH, 30s N, 30s Z repeated. below can still see few scattered w. Ci thickening
11:41							Can still see w plus Sun shining through Ci above.
11:45	32 kft.						Ci thinning below.
11:47	32 kft.		0		70.9	30.4	thickening below (using lidar)
11:50							Contracting.
11:55:06	R1.1						Start on. (FL320) Optically thin above + below.
12:00:04	R1.1 end.		0		70.7	30.1	Turning. Still inside cloud.
12:03:07	P1.1 ↓						descend at 600ft./min from FL320
12:07:52	P1.1 end. (FL300)		0		70.6	30.9	very thin Ci below.
12:15							turning. v. thin Ci below thicker above. (by eye)

ARIES flight log

Flight: B503

page 2 of 3

Date: 25/01/10

Operator(s): CLARE LEE

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B:2

Loc./Notes: CONSTRAIN

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
12:24:48	R1.3			0	70.7	31.2	Run at FL280 very thin Ci below - cloud base 26.1 left (from lidar) turning to right.
12:29:49	R1.3 end						
12:39:08	R1.4 FL260			0	70.7	30.7	Below cloud. (see cloud phys. measuring bits cloud.) - clear below on lidar. Sheet W ahead. Ascending back into cloud.
12:45:09	R1.4 end P2 ↑						
12:48		Nadir long		C			Closing shutter in ascent. Inim CH, 3min N repeat. Script hung - reset. Cloud increasing below as increasing height.
12:51							
12:59	FL330 ↑ CANVZSD			0			Request for zenith view. CANVZSD 30s CH, 30s N, 30s Z Contrailing
13:01:10							Thickening up below.
13:07	FL360 ↑						Broken W below. (5/8) seen on lidar.
13:11							Thinner to N.E. Turning back W.
13:15							
13:19:00	R2.1 (FL350)			0	70.8	30.5	Run at max alt. Ci still above. CPL seeing thin plates. Can't see ground. lidar out. at 254ft.
13:40:11	P Jend (FL330)						In thick Ci T=-54
13:45:41							Thinner below. (5/8 W below) doing spiral descent Stopped contrailing
13:54:56	FL314 ↓						
14:26:08				0	70.5	29.9	
14:39	FL250			0	70.7	30.2	

ARIES flight log

Flight: *B503*

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Date: *25/01/10*

Operator(s): *CLARE LEE*

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: *CONSTRAIN*

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
<i>14:44:33</i>				<i>C</i>	<i>70.9</i>	<i>30.8</i>	<i>Closing shutter to check stability of spectra.</i>
<i>14:47:53</i>				<i>O</i>			<i>Open shutter again.</i>
<i>15:07:00</i>				<i>O</i>	<i>70.7</i>	<i>30.2</i>	
<i>15:20</i>	<i>FL350</i>				<i>70.8</i>	<i>30.5</i>	<i>In Cims - can just see through above? + below.</i>
<i>15:27:16</i>	<i>FL350.</i>			<i>C</i>	<i>70.8</i>	<i>29.9</i>	<i>Closing shutter to check stability. zenith are looking a bit odd maybe thick Ci</i>
<i>15:28:31</i>				<i>C</i>			<i>Viewing shutter in zenith view.</i>
<i>15:30:07</i>				<i>O</i>			<i>Opening at end nadir view. Ci thinning below</i>
							<i>changing speed for cal in dual tests.</i>
<i>15:34:10</i>				<i>C</i>			<i>shutter closed. for non-zenith</i>
<i>15:35:45</i>				<i>O</i>			
<i>15:36:32</i>				<i>C</i>			
<i>15:37:44</i>				<i>O</i>			<i>Leaving open.</i>
<i>15:38:01</i>	<i>RL4 (FL370)</i>			<i>O</i>	<i>71.0</i>	<i>30.0</i>	
<i>15:43</i>				<i>C</i>			<i>Stopped data taking</i>

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 25.01.10

Flight No: B 508

Pre-Flighter: STEFIE Cowan

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
1	✓	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
2	✓	Core Chemistry	Enter cyl content press	N ₂ = 30 bar CO ₂ /Ar = 138 bar
3	✓	Core Chemistry	Driers OK	
4	✓	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
5	✓	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
6	✓	Core Chemistry	All Flows Checked OK	
7	✓	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
8	✓	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
9	✓	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
10	✓	HORACE	Recording data	
11	✓	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
12	✓	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
13	✓	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
14	✓	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
15	✓	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
16	✓	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
17	✓	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	
18	✓	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
19	✓	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
20	✓	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
21	✓	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
22	✓	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
23	✓	Satcom C	Checked	In cockpit
24	✓	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
25	x	CNC	Butanol filled	
26	x	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
27	x	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	
28	x	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	
29	x	3786 CPC	DI Checked / Topped up	

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
30	x	CCN Water	Supply filled / Drain empty	
31	x	CCN SS cols A & B	Set to manual A0.2, B0.1	
32	x	CCN Pressure	Normally set to 650mb	
33	x	CCN Flow Ratios	A & B = 10 ± 0.3	
34	x	3786 CPC	Drained	
35	x	CPC Laptop	AIM Software set up	
36		Core Chemistry	O ₃ /NO _x /CO zeros performed Ok	
<u>External Checks</u>				
37	✓	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
38	✓	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
39	✓	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
40	✓	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
41	✓	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
42	✓	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
43	✓	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
44	x	WAS Bottles	No. fitted and position.	
45	✓	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
46	✓	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
47	✓	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
48	✓	All other covers	Removed	
49	✓	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
50		Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
51	✓	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
52	✓	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		Signed
53	✓	ICEX applied		
54	✓	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -	a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more	

Cloud Physics Flight Log B503

Date:17/01/2010	Operator: MAP	DRS Time:08:30:00	DAU1 Time:same	DAU2 Time:same	AUX1 Time:same	AUX2 Time:same
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DAU2 Disk space?

	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		CIP-15		SID2+SID3		2DC	
Operated?	Y		Y		Y		Y		Y		y	
Pre-flight checks	Ref V:	3.14	Vref (>7V):	5.4	El#1 V (>1):	0.7	El#1 V (>1):	3.15	Comms2?:	y	El#1 V (>1):	-0.7
	Data TX?	Y	Sample flow	1.15	El#32 V (>1):	2.1	El#32 V (>1):	3.6	Comms2?:	Y	El#32 V (>1):	-0.7
			Sheath flow	14.25	El#64 V (>1)	0.5	El#64 V (>1)	3.15				
			Spectra ok?	N								

Just after take-off	Are SAMPLE and RECORD buttons on PADS both green?	Y	Are all heaters on? (Check ammeters and CIP dummy box heater switch).	y
	Are all PADS instruments enabled and updating?	Y		

NOTE that CTRL+T will insert the current time where the cursor is as long as the cursor is a cursor and not a selected box.

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/L	Max R			
08:32:37			15	Noise								
08:33:02			20									
08:34:42			30									
08:35:51			40									
11:55:04	FL320											Start Run 1.1
11:56:00		0.01	35			0.0007		45	175	10	0.5	
11:58:00						0.0007		40	325	10	0.5	
12:00:03												End of Run
12:03:01	FL320					0.0002		20	175	10	0.2	Start Profile 1.1
12:05:45	FL310					0.0012		55	150	10	0.4	
12:07:51	FL300					0.002		45	175	10	0.5	End of Profile
12:10:16	FL300											Start Run 1.2
12:11:00		0.01	45			0.002		30	250	10	0.7	
12:13:00						0.0005		30	250	10	0.4	
12:15:16	FL300											End of Run
12:17:32	FL300	0.01	45			0.0005		75	150	10	05	Start Profile 1.2

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/L	Max R			
12:20:12	FL290	0.01	45			0.0015		40	175	10	0.6	
12:22:33	FL280					0.003		30	200	10	0.5	End of Profile
12:24:48	FL280											Start Run 1.3
12:25:00		0.01	45			0.004		38	300	10	0.6	
12:27:00		0.04	45			0.003		40	200	10	0.6	
12:29:51	FL280											End of Run
12:31:55	FL280					0.0001		35	175	10	0.7	Start Profile 1.3
12:34:42	FL270	0.03	40			0.0001		10	175	10	0.3	
12:37:03	FL260											End of profile
12:39:11	FL260											Start Run 1.4
12:40:00						0.0001		1			0.1	
12:42:00											0.1	
12:44:00												
12:45:09	FL260											End of Run & Start Profile 2
12:46:48	FL270										0.1	
12:48:22	FL280	0.01	40			0.0002		30	175	10	0.6	
12:50:06	FL290	0.01	40			0.001		20	175	10	0.4	
12:51:34	FL300					0.0006		35	200	10	0.2	
12:53:38	FL310					0.0002		30	150	10	0.4	
12:55:36	FL320					0.0001		25	125	10	0.6	
12:57:57	FL330					0.0001		35	125	10	0.5	End of Profile
13:03:55	FL330											Continue Profile 2
13:05:51	FL340					0.001		40	150	10	0.3	End of Profile 2
13:16:49	FL340	0.01	40			0.0001		50	125	11	1	Start Profile 3
13:18:52	FL350											End of Profile & Start Run 2
13:19:00		0.02	40					15	125	11	1	
13:21:00		0.02	40					30	100	11	2	
13:23:00		0.02	40					10	100	11	1.5	
13:24:37												
13:27:37	FL350											Start Run 2.1
13:28:00		0.04	40					25	100	11	1	
13:30:00		0.04	40					30	125	11	0.5	
13:32:14												End of Run 2.1
13:35:19	FL350	0.04	40					Noisy			2.5	Start Profile 4.1
13:38:12	FL340	0.04	40			0.0001		Noisy			1	Rearm 0 1
13:40:11	FL330	0.02	40			0.0001		35	125	11	1	End of Profile

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/L	Max R			
13:42:34	FL330											Start Run 2.2
13:43:00		0.02	30					60	125	11	1.5	Rearm 0 64
13:45:00		0.02	35					35	150	10	0.5	
13:47:55	FL330											End of Run
13:50:24	FL330											Start profile 4.2
13:51:00		0.03	45					45	100	11	1	2DC slightly noisy
13:53:00		0.03	40					25	125	11	1	
13:55:27	FL310					0.0001		20	150	10	0.4	End of Profile
13:57:39	FL310											Start Run 2.3
13:58:00						0.0001		38	125	11	0.3	
14:00:00		0.03	40			0.0001		26	125	11	1	
14:02:00		0.03	40			0.0003		50	150	10	1.5	
14:02:40	FL310											End of Run
14:04:55	FL310					0.0002		28	150	10	0.3	Start Profile 4.3
14:07:18	FL300							25	125	11	0.5	
14:09:51	FL290							7	125	11	0.1	End of Run
14:12:03	FL290											Start Run 2.4
14:13:00		0.02	40			0.0002		6	125	11	0.25	
14:15:00		0.02	40					25	125	11	0.5	
14:17:09	FL290											End of Run
14:19:13	FL290					0.007		50	150	10	1	Start Profile 4.4
14:21:46	FL280					0.0001		35	175	10	0.4	
14:23:48	FL270					0.0001		15	175	10	0.3	End of Run
14:25:59	FL270											Start Run 2.5
14:26:00								7	150	10	0.2	
14:28:00								25	150	10	0.2	
14:30:00						0.0015		45	175	10	0.4	
14:31:58												End of Run
14:33:47	FL270											Start Profile 4.5
14:35:45	FL260					0.007		45	225	10	0.1	
14:38:51	FL250							1	200	10	0.1	End of Profile
14:41:05	FL250											Start Run 2.6
14:42:00						0.007		1	200	10	0.2	
14:44:00								20	200	10	05	
14:46:38	FL250											End of Run
14:48:37	FL250											Start Profile 4.6

Cloud Physics Flight Log B503

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/L	Max R			
14:50:51	FL240											
14:53:07	FL230											End of Profile
14:55:06	FL230											Start Run 2.7
14:56:00												
14:58:00												
15:00:00												
15:01:17	FL230											End of Run
15:03:00	FL230											Start Profile 4.7
15:03:58	FL240											
15:05:20	FL250					0.004		45	200	10	0.6	
15:06:12	FL260					0.004		60	200	10	0.8	
15:07:11	FL270					0.004		20	200	10	0.2	
15:08:10	FL280					0.002		23	175	10	0.1	End of Profile
15:10:19	FL280					0.002		90	150	10	0.6	Start Profile 4.8
15:11:32	FL290					0.0005		55	200	10	0.2	
15:12:27	FL300					0.0001		70	125	11	1.2	
15:13:20	FL310					0.0001		25	175	10	0.1	
15:14:38	FL320					0.0001		40	150	10	0.5	
15:15:57	FL330					0.0001		68	125	11	4	End of Profile
15:18:19	FL330					0.0005		150	150	10	20	Start Profile 4.9
15:19:35	FL340					0.0001		40	125	11	4	
15:21:21	FL350											End of Profile & Start Run 3
15:22:00		0.1	40					20	100	11	4	
15:24:00		0.1	40					20	125	11	4	
15:26:00		0.1	40					Noisy			4	
15:28:00		0.1	40					Noisy			1	Rearm 0 1
15:30:00		0.1	40					Noisy			2	
15:32:00		0.1	40					Noisy			2	
15:34:00		0.1	40					Noisy			2	
15:34:40	FL350							Noisy				End of Run 3 & Start Profile 5
15:35:37	FL340							Noisy			40	
15:36:50	FL330					0.0001		Noisy			1	
15:38:01	FL320					0.0016		Noisy			0.1	End of Profile & Start Run 4
15:39:00						0.0012		Noisy			0.4	
15:41:00						0.0005		Noisy			0.2	
15:43:00						0.0001		Noisy			0.1	

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B503	Date	25 01 2010	Operator	Angela Dean	Page No.	1 of 1
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GMT	Sonde No.	Event <i>eg land, splashdown</i>	Comments <i>pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
11:49:12	1	Launch	274.20 -51.60 98.84 333.30 29.90 0.80 -3.883400 58.743000 9760.00
12:01:02	1	Land	9999.00 99.00 11.41 163.28 10.19 -9.12 -3.833780 58.724829
			End drop time changed from 718.1 to 709.6, end pressure changed from 1035.9 to 1035.2.
			Surface alt unknown NOT ticked
13:30:03	2	Launch	238.00 -59.40 100.00 329.40 36.50 0.90 -3.718200 59.234500 10679.00 0
13:42:27	2	Land	1033.60 3.65 65.19 175.75 13.58 -10.20 -3.623534 59.210679 -75.82 6
			Surface alt unknown NOT ticked
	3	Launch	
	3	Land	
			End drop time override Surface alt unknown ticked

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B503

Date: 25 Jan 10

Instruments

1. Nevz TWC only
2. Recording started with wrong (yesterday's flight no - B502). Stopped at 0920 and started with B503.
3. FM Monitor display - strange colour effects on windows.
4. Network – intermittent operation at aft core console. Moved Ethernet input on hub (red lead) to another port, then okay.
5. NO / Nox – reading 3.1 /4.2 during zero on pre-flight
6. CO signal dropped to zero after take-off. Did cal after t/o, didn't go to zero. Tried another cal, then okay.
7. 2DC – problems at high (cold, -60C) level
8. Printer – poor quality plots, text in black/blue and red. All cartridges in drawer open (used?)
9. VIRC – tries to open but immediately bombs out
10. BBRs – Upper pyrogeometer signal noisy
- 11.

Aircraft

- 1.

Satcom

MPDS – 2 x satpics

Satcom H – not used

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Choose A Flight Number To Show Instrument Status For It

Key :

 Choose Flight
[back](#)

B503
Primary Systems

AMTG	<input type="checkbox"/>
AVAPS	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cabin Pressure Rmount	<input type="checkbox"/>
Camera - Downward Facing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Camera - Forward Facing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Camera - Rearward Facing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Camera - Upward Facing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cruciform GPS	<input type="checkbox"/>
DLU AERACK	<input type="checkbox"/>
DLU BBR Lower	<input type="checkbox"/>
DLU BBR Upper	<input type="checkbox"/>
DLU Core Chem	<input type="checkbox"/>
DLU Core Consoles	<input type="checkbox"/>
DLU Port Aft	<input type="checkbox"/>
DLU Port Fwd	<input type="checkbox"/>
DLU Stbd Fwd	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fax machine	<input type="checkbox"/>
GIN Applanix POSAV510	<input type="checkbox"/>
-----	<input type="checkbox"/>

Temperature

Cabin Temperature	<input type="checkbox"/>
Heimann	<input type="checkbox"/>
Rosemount DIT	<input type="checkbox"/>
Rosemount NDIT	<input type="checkbox"/>
Hygrometry	
Buck CR2	<input type="checkbox"/>
FWVS	<input type="checkbox"/>
General Eastern	<input type="checkbox"/>
Total Water Probe	<input type="checkbox"/>
SAW Hygrometer	<input type="checkbox"/>

Remote Sensing

BBR (clear) Lower	<input type="checkbox"/>
BBR (clear) Upper	<input type="checkbox"/>
BBR (IR) Lower	<input type="checkbox"/>
BBR (IR) Upper	<input type="checkbox"/>
BBR (red) Lower	<input type="checkbox"/>
BBR (red) Upper	<input type="checkbox"/>
ARIES	<input type="checkbox"/>
CASI/ATM	<input type="checkbox"/>
DEIMOS	<input type="checkbox"/>
IR Camera	<input type="checkbox"/>
JNO2 Photometer Lower	<input type="checkbox"/>
JNO2 Photometer Upper	<input type="checkbox"/>
JO1D Photometer Lower	<input type="checkbox"/>
JO1D Photometer Upper	<input type="checkbox"/>
LIDAR	<input type="checkbox"/>
MARSS	<input type="checkbox"/>
Mini-LIDAR	<input type="checkbox"/>
SHIMS Lower	<input type="checkbox"/>
-----	<input type="checkbox"/>

Cloud Physics

2DC	<input type="checkbox"/>
2DP	<input type="checkbox"/>
FFSSP	<input type="checkbox"/>
Johnson Williams	<input type="checkbox"/>
Nevzorov	<input type="checkbox"/>
2DS	<input type="checkbox"/>
ADA	<input type="checkbox"/>
CAPS	<input type="checkbox"/>
CDP (Canister)	<input type="checkbox"/>
CDP (Fuselage)	<input type="checkbox"/>
CIP 100	<input type="checkbox"/>
CIP 25	<input type="checkbox"/>
CPI	<input type="checkbox"/>
FSSP (UMan)	<input type="checkbox"/>
INC	<input type="checkbox"/>
SID1	<input type="checkbox"/>
SID2	<input type="checkbox"/>
SID3	<input type="checkbox"/>
-----	<input type="checkbox"/>

Printer							
Radar Altimeter							
RVSM IAS							
RVSM Static Pressure							
S9 Static Press Rmount							
Satcom Phones							
Satcom Data							
Turb Diff Centre- Static							
Turb Diff Left-Right							
Turb Diff Up-Down							
Turb Horizontal Check							
Turb Vertical Check							
Weather Radar							
XR5 GPS							

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 25 Jan 2010 1300 UTC


```
*** Opened channel log for #faam146 at 25/01/2010 10:37:52
[2010/01/25 10:37] *** FAAMDepOpsNetbo (DougA@i.love.debian.org) has joined #faam146
[2010/01/25 10:45] <FAAM_Woolley> hello
[2010/01/25 14:20] *** FAAM_fit_man (GLUXE@i.love.debian.org) has joined #faam146
[2010/01/25 14:21] <FAAM_fit_man> hello
[2010/01/25 14:21] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] Hello FitMan
[2010/01/25 14:21] <FAAM_fit_man> ..just found you have to disable the firewall to get VIRC working here
[2010/01/25 14:21] <FAAM_fit_man> ETA 1600
[2010/01/25 14:21] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] On the video PC?
[2010/01/25 14:22] <FAAM_fit_man> yes
[2010/01/25 14:22] <FAAM_fit_man> sorry, on the fm pc
[2010/01/25 14:22] <FAAM_Woolley> i never had to do that...!
[2010/01/25 14:22] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] Menu for tonight isHot Roast Salmon (served warm on a salad of Fine Beans, Black Olives and Quails Eggs)
[2010/01/25 14:22] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] -----
[2010/01/25 14:22] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] Gateaux of Haggis, Neeps and Tatties (served with a Grain Mustard Sauce)
[2010/01/25 14:22] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] -----
[2010/01/25 14:22] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] Steamed Orange Marmalade Whisky Pudding (with AVmilla Ice Cream)
[2010/01/25 14:22] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] -----
[2010/01/25 14:22] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] Freshly Brewed Coffee (served with Vanilla Fudge)
[2010/01/25 14:22] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] -----
[2010/01/25 14:22] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] £25 per person
[2010/01/25 14:23] <FAAM_fit_man> yum yum, what do the veggies get?
[2010/01/25 14:23] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] Do Keith and Clare want sausages? Veggies get Veggie haggis
[2010/01/25 14:24] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] Any alteration toMo Smith Haggis, neeps and tatties
[2010/01/25 14:24] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] Doug Anderson Haggis, neeps and tatties
[2010/01/25 14:24] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] Alan Woolley Haggis, neeps and tatties
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[2010/01/25 14:24] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] Angela Dean Haggis, neeps and tatties
[2010/01/25 14:24] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] Alan Foster Haggis, neeps and tatties
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[2010/01/25 14:24] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] Kirsty McBeath Haggis, neeps and tatties
[2010/01/25 14:24] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] Martyn Pickering Haggis with rice
[2010/01/25 14:24] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] James Dorsey Veg Haggis
[2010/01/25 14:24] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] Joseph Ulanowski Veg Haggis
[2010/01/25 14:24] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] Clare Lee Other option
[2010/01/25 14:24] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] Keith Bower Other option
[2010/01/25 14:24] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] Robbie Voaden tbc - Haggis, neeps and tatties
[2010/01/25 14:27] <FAAM_fit_man> what time is dinner?
[2010/01/25 14:27] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] 19:30
[2010/01/25 14:29] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] Any problems with AVAPS data recording PC?
[2010/01/25 14:33] <FAAM_fit_man> no probs with avaps pc
[2010/01/25 14:36] <FAAM_fit_man> KB and JD and CL want something other than veg, haggis or sausages if at all possible
[2010/01/25 14:36] <FAAM_fit_man> something a little more inspiring...
[2010/01/25 14:37] <FAAM_Woolley> not sure where doug has gone, but I'll draw that to his attention
[2010/01/25 14:37] <FAAM_fit_man> thanks Alan
[2010/01/25 14:39] <FAAM_fit_man> Alan, the FM monitor colour scheme is very odd, is this "normal"
[2010/01/25 14:40] <FAAM_Woolley> It started when Franco asked me to check that the lidar display pc could be vnc'd
[2010/01/25 14:40] <FAAM_Woolley> it's very annoying
[2010/01/25 14:41] <FAAM_Woolley> it may be a case of needing to explore the display options or something
[2010/01/25 14:44] <FAAM_fit_man> i agree!
[2010/01/25 14:48] <FAAM_fit_man> i've tried a few alternative display schemes but haven't found anything like it used to be
[2010/01/25 14:49] <FAAM_Woolley> we could take a look on wednesday if we're on the ground
[2010/01/25 14:50] <FAAM_fit_man> is that sounding likely?
[2010/01/25 14:51] <FAAM_Woolley> well, it's hearsay based on the forecasts and listening to Phil Brown, but maybe...
[2010/01/25 14:55] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] Back with my apple for lunch. Has JD changed his mind since this morning? I thought sausages was mentioned this morning too. Do they want food off the normal main course menu? Or something like a breast o' ee sleekit, cow'rin, tim'rous beastie?
[2010/01/25 14:56] <FAAM_fit_man> they are very fickle
[2010/01/25 14:57] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] They may be rather peckish come late this evening then
[2010/01/25 15:00] <FAAM_fit_man> yes, once we start the transit, i'll try to get something more definite
[2010/01/25 15:01] <FAAM_fit_man> JD DOES want veggie haggis! 2 to go
[2010/01/25 15:04] <FAAM_fit_man> CL and KB would like piece of chicken breast if pos
[2010/01/25 15:04] <FAAM_fit_man> ..each
[2010/01/25 15:05] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] Not moose breast then?
[2010/01/25 15:06] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] Piper arranged - 50 quid on top of bill. How will we pay?
[2010/01/25 15:06] <FAAM_fit_man> we'll all have to chip in
[2010/01/25 15:25] <FAAM_fit_man> just about finished the science now, ETA still 1600
[2010/01/25 15:25] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] Copy, Engs and PC on their way to the airport now.
[2010/01/25 15:25] <FAAM_fit_man> ok
[2010/01/25 15:26] <FAAM_fit_man> are we having a meeting?
[2010/01/25 15:27] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] 17:30?
[2010/01/25 15:27] <FAAM_fit_man> yep, should be okay
[2010/01/25 15:39] <FAAM_fit_man> signing off now
[2010/01/25 15:39] *** FAAM_fit_man (GLUXE@i.love.debian.org) has left #faam146
[2010/01/25 16:33] *** FAAM_Woolley (alan@i.love.debian.org) has quit IRC [Ping timeout: 600 seconds]
[2010/01/25 17:38] *** james (james@i.love.debian.org) has joined #faam146
[2010/01/25 17:38] <james> Hi Mo!
[2010/01/25 17:39] *** james (james@i.love.debian.org) has left #faam146 [Konversation terminated!]
*** Closed channel log for #faam146 at 25/01/2010 17:50:30
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[2010/01/25 14:29] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] Any problems with AVAPS data recording PC?
[2010/01/25 14:33] <FAAM_fit_man> no probs with avaps pc
[2010/01/25 14:36] <FAAM_fit_man> KB and JD and CL want something other than veg, haggis or sausages if at all possible
[2010/01/25 14:36] <FAAM_fit_man> something a little more inspiring...
[2010/01/25 14:37] <FAAM_Woolley> not sure where doug has gone, but I'll draw that to his attention
[2010/01/25 14:37] <FAAM_fit_man> thanks Alan
[2010/01/25 14:39] <FAAM_fit_man> Alan, the FM monitor colour scheme is very odd, is this "normal"
[2010/01/25 14:40] <FAAM_Woolley> It started when Franco asked me to check that the lidar display pc could be vnc'd
[2010/01/25 14:40] <FAAM_Woolley> it's very annoying
[2010/01/25 14:41] <FAAM_Woolley> it may be a case of needing to explore the display options or something
[2010/01/25 14:44] <FAAM_fit_man> i agree!
[2010/01/25 14:48] <FAAM_fit_man> i've tried a few alternative display schemes but haven't found anything like it used to be
[2010/01/25 14:49] <FAAM_Woolley> we could take a look on wednesday if we're on the ground
[2010/01/25 14:50] <FAAM_fit_man> is that sounding likely?
[2010/01/25 14:51] <FAAM_Woolley> well, it's hearsay based on the forecasts and listening to Phil Brown, but maybe...
[2010/01/25 14:55] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] Back with my apple for lunch. Has JD changed his mind since this morning? I thought sausages was mentioned this morning too. Do they want food off the normal main course menu? Or something like a breast o' ee sleekit, cow'rin, tim'rous beastie?
[2010/01/25 14:56] <FAAM_fit_man> they are very fickle
[2010/01/25 14:57] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] They may be rather peckish come late this evening then
[2010/01/25 15:00] <FAAM_fit_man> yes, once we start the transit, i'll try to get something more definite
[2010/01/25 15:01] <FAAM_fit_man> JD DOES want veggie haggis! 2 to go
[2010/01/25 15:04] <FAAM_fit_man> CL and KB would like piece of chicken breast if pos
[2010/01/25 15:04] <FAAM_fit_man> ..each
[2010/01/25 15:05] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] Not moose breast then?
[2010/01/25 15:06] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] Piper arranged - 50 quid on top of bill. How will we pay?
[2010/01/25 15:06] <FAAM_fit_man> we'll all have to chip in
[2010/01/25 15:25] <FAAM_fit_man> just about finished the science now, ETA still 1600
[2010/01/25 15:25] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] Copy, Engs and PC on their way to the airport now.
[2010/01/25 15:25] <FAAM_fit_man> ok
[2010/01/25 15:26] <FAAM_fit_man> are we having a meeting?
[2010/01/25 15:27] [FAAMDepOpsNetbo] 17:30?
[2010/01/25 15:27] <FAAM_fit_man> yep, should be okay
[2010/01/25 15:39] <FAAM_fit_man> signing off now
[2010/01/25 15:39] *** FAAM_fit_man (GLUXE@i.love.debian.org) has left #faam146
[2010/01/25 16:33] *** FAAM_Woolley (alan@i.love.debian.org) has quit IRC [Ping timeout: 600 seconds]
[2010/01/25 17:38] *** james (james@i.love.debian.org) has joined #faam146
[2010/01/25 17:38] <james> Hi Mo!
[2010/01/25 17:39] *** james (james@i.love.debian.org) has left #faam146 [Konversation terminated!]
*** Closed channel log for #faam146 at 25/01/2010 17:50:30
```

B503 - 25/01/10 - Angela Dean

In-Flight CO Calibrations

Please log fluorescence cell temperature and pressure immediately following calibration. During warm cabin flights, temperature can reach 40°C. During flight levels >FL020, cell pressure will drop (down to 5.9 at FL030)

		<i>Nominally 66 Hz/ppbv</i>	<i>Nominally 34000 Hz</i>	<i>Nominally 7.5 Torr</i>	<i>Nominally 35 - 40 °C</i>
Time	Flight level	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbv)	Background Count (Hz)	Cell Pressure (Torr)	Lamp Temp (°C)
01/24/2010 15:51:40	Previous Flight	65.227	33306.23	N/A	N/A
01/25/2010 10:26:44	Pre-Flight/Gnd	-0.188	34933.37	7.54s	35.49
01/25/2010 11:18:54	19.0kft	67.695	33042.07	5.83s	35.57
01/25/2010 11:38:08	31kft	66.347	32515.60	5.90s	38.96
01/25/2010 13:01:05	33kft	65.427	32215.23	5.62s	40.10
01/25/2010 13:49:55	33.1kft	65.261	32134.03	5.88s	40.50
01/25/2010 14:40:03	25kft	65.736	32236.17	6.08	39.64
01/25/2010 15:31:08	35kft	65.710	32407.33	5.75s?	40.50
Time	Flight level	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbv)	Background Count (Hz)	Cell Pressure (Torr)	Lamp Temp (°C)

Pre-Flight & In-Flight comments/faults report

CO Monitor averaged zero (either in Hz or ppbv) : _____
 NOx monitor averaged zero (ppbv) : _____
 Ozone Monitor averaged zero (ppbv) : _____

CO Calibrations on automatic repeat? : NO Interval set? N/A

O3/NOx filter zero started: 09:46 ended 10:16
 CO zero started: 09:46 ended 10:18

Problem with CO... Zero stopped at 10:18. Pre-flight cal started approx 10:20. CO plot is showing 0 - flat lined (as if still zeroed). Zero confirmed definitely off via hyperterminal and display screen. In flight cal completed at 11:18. Very slow to start cal; approx 40 second delay. Cal peak on plot not zero after. Values post-cal read ~90 ppb (at ~28 kft). Second in flight cal appeared more normal. Values normal. 'Sens' etc normal values. Zeroing was left on for half an hour due to delay in security. Therefore may have taken longer to recover...? Maybe...?

Also - NOx averages during Zero were way too high; approx +3.14. Possibly needs filter changing/cleaning?

post flight content pressure values: O3 145 & NOx 35

B503 - 25/01/10 - Angela Dean

In-Flight CO Calibrations

Please log fluorescence cell temperature and pressure immediately following calibration. During warm cabin flights, temperature can reach 40°C. During flight levels >FL020, cell pressure will drop (down to 5.9 at FL030)

		<i>Nominally 66 Hz/ppbv</i>	<i>Nominally 34000 Hz</i>	<i>Nominally 7.5 Torr</i>	<i>Nominally 35 - 40 °C</i>
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01/25/2010 13:01:05	33kft	65.427	32215.23	5.62s	40.10
01/25/2010 13:49:55	33.1kft	65.261	32134.03	5.88s	40.50
01/25/2010 14:40:03	25kft	65.736	32236.17	6.08	39.64
01/25/2010 15:31:08	35kft	65.710	32407.33	5.75s?	40.50
Time	Flight level	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbv)	Background Count (Hz)	Cell Pressure (Torr)	Lamp Temp (°C)

Pre-Flight & In-Flight comments/faults report

CO Monitor averaged zero (either in Hz or ppbv)	:	_____
NOx monitor averaged zero (ppbv)	:	_____
Ozone Monitor averaged zero (ppbv)	:	_____
CO Calibrations on automatic repeat?	:	NO Interval set? N/A
O3/NOx filter zero started: 09:46 ended 10:16		
CO zero started: 09:46 ended 10:18		
<p>Problem with CO... Zero stopped at 10:18. Pre-flight cal started approx 10:20. CO plot is showing 0 - flat lined (as if still zeroed). Zero confirmed definately off via hyperterminal and display screen. In flight cal completed at 11:18. Very slow to start cal; approx 40 second delay. Cal peak on plot did not zero after. Values post-cal read ~90 ppb (at ~28 kft). Second in flight cal appeared more normal. Values normal. 'Sens' etc normal values. Zeroing was left on for half an hour due to delay in security. Therefore may have taken longer to recover...? Maybe...?</p>		
Also - NOx averages during Zero were way too high; approx +3.14. Possibly needs filter changing/cleaning?		
post flight content pressure values: O3 145 & NOx 35		

EIEB51 MSG 10.8 micron Infrared Image 25 Jan 2010 1300 UTC

151019	151558	Profile 4.8	28.1 - 33.0 kft	049
151402		Event	31.6 kft	055 Contrailing
151815	152124	Profile 4.9	33.1 - 35.0 kft	226
152142	153429	Run 3	35.0 kft	234 CVI run 200KIAS
152759		Event	35.1 kft	247 Accel to 220KIAS
152944		Event	35.0 kft	246 Steady at 220KIAS
153429	153801	Profile 5	35.0 - 32.0 kft	246
153801	154944	Run 4	32.0 - 32.1 kft	243
154318		Event	32.0 kft	222 Reduce to 220KIAS
154406		Event	32.0 kft	214 Reduce to 190KIAS
154500		Event	32.0 kft	216 Steady at 190KIAS
160929		Land	-.60 kft	272 Prestwick
161145		ASP	-.61 kft	243 Closed

Range corrected signal - 36 profiles

Ch0

Ch1

Range corrected signal - 36 profiles

Ch0

Ch1

Range corrected signal - 36 profiles

Ch0

Ch1

Time after midnight (minutes)

Range corrected signal - 36 profiles

Ch0

Ch1

Time after midnight (minutes)

Range corrected signal - 36 profiles

Ch0

Ch1

Range corrected signal - 36 profiles

Ch0

Ch1

Time after midnight (minutes)

Range corrected signal - 30 profiles

Ch0

Ch1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(514982 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(520573 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(526090 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(661970 Msgs)

Range: 20
 STABILIZATION FAULT
 Gain: Max
 WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(667246 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(805613 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(810902 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(816141 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(821391 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(826583 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(831798 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(837043 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(842284 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(847541 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(852698 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(857956 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(863188 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(868442 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(873586 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(878851 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(884339 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(889778 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(895242 Msgs)

Radarscope controls including 'Search' (Define, Back, Fwd), 'Step' (Back, Fwd, 25), and 'Data Accept' (Filter, 1).

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(900730 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(906217 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(911634 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(917100 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(922583 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(928073 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(933494 Msgs)

Radar Pads
 Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
 Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
 Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
 STABILIZATION FAULT
 Gain: Max
 WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(938958 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(944461 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(949887 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(955350 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(960825 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(966315 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(971744 Msgs)

Search:
 Step:
 Data Accept: Filter

Range: 20
 STABILIZATION FAULT
 Gain: Max
 WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(977207 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(982697 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(988136 Msgs)

Range: 20
 STABILIZATION FAULT
 Gain: Max
 WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(993600 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(999086 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1004529 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1009993 Msgs)

Range: 20
 STABILIZATION FAULT
 Gain: Max
 WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1015474 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1020968 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1026385 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1031850 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1037334 Msgs)

Range: 20
 STABILIZATION FAULT
 Gain: Max
 WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1042820 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1048243 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1053707 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1059192 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1064685 Msgs)

Radarscope controls: Radar, Paste, Search (Define, Back, Fwd), Step (Back, Fwd, 25), Data Accept (Filter, 1)

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1070101 Msgs)

Radarscope controls including 'Radarscope' button, 'Search' (Define, Back, Fwd), 'Step' (Back, Fwd, 25), and 'Data Accept' (Filter, 1).

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1075565 Msgs)

Range: 20
 STABILIZATION FAULT
 Gain: Max
 WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1081052 Msgs)

Radarscope controls including 'Search' (Define, Back, Fwd), 'Step' (Back, Fwd, 25), and 'Data Accept' (Filter, 1) buttons.

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1086538 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1091958 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1097446 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1102888 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1108352 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1113854 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1119282 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1124774 Msgs)

Radar Pads
 Search: Define Back Fwd
 Step: Back Fwd 25
 Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
 STABILIZATION FAULT
 Gain: Max
 WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1130212 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1135675 Msgs)

Range: 20
 STABILIZATION FAULT
 Gain: Max
 WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1141184 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1146604 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1152069 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1157572 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
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Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1162998 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1168462 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1173971 Msgs)

Radar Radar
 Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
 Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
 Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
 STABILIZATION FAULT
 Gain: Max
 WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1179391 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1184878 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1190320 Msgs)

Radar Paste
 Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
 Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
 Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
 STABILIZATION FAULT
 Gain: Max
 WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1195785 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1201268 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1206713 Msgs)

Range: 20
 STABILIZATION FAULT
 Gain: Max
 WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1212179 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1217678 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1223108 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1228588 Msgs)

Search:
 Step:
 Data Accept: Filter

Range: 20
 STABILIZATION FAULT
 Gain: Max
 WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1234036 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1239500 Msgs)

Radar Pads
 Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
 Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
 Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
 STABILIZATION FAULT
 Gain: Max
 WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1244966 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1250430 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1255914 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1261408 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1266824 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1272288 Msgs)

Range: 20
 STABILIZATION FAULT
 Gain: Max
 WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1277788 Msgs)

Radar Paste
 Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
 Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
 Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
 STABILIZATION FAULT
 Gain: Max
 WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1283217 Msgs)

Range: 20
 STABILIZATION FAULT
 Gain: Max
 WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1288681 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1294185 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(1299610 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(2317383 Msgs)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(2322868 Msgs)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

5 10 15 20

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(2342132 Msgs)

Radar Search Step 25 Data Accept Filter 1

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(2347687 Msgs)

Filter

Range: 20
 STABILIZATION FAULT
 Gain: Max
 WX

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 (7422 Msgs)
 - Dataset2 (1896 Msgs)
 - Dataset3 (8719 Msgs)
 - Dataset4 (18386 Msgs)
 - Dataset5 - Recording(2353152 Msgs)

Radar Filter

Range: 20
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

